

Table 4. Characteristic of the studies analysed

Research	Physical/ Cognitive Variables	Study Duration Sample/ Country	design/ Age/	Procedure and activities measures.	physical Cognitive function measures	Result
[24]	CRF/AP	Cross-sectional study/ 1725 students/ 5th grade and 7th grade/ Virginia, USA		Cardiorespiratory fitness: Students did the Progressive Aerobic Cardiovascular Endurance Run (PACER) used in FitnessGram. This test measures the time it takes the child to run or walk 1 mile. With the PACER assessment, the student is expected to run back and forth across a 20-metre space at a pace defined on a beep-only or music audiotape, which gets faster each minute.	Academic performance: WESTEST (West Virginia Educational Standards Test) 4 test areas: mathematics, science, social studies, and reading and language arts.	Students who had better marks on the CRF test obtained significantly higher WESTEST scores than students who had lower CRF capacity.

[42]	PA and CRF/AP	Cross-sectional study/ 687 students/ 2 nd and 3 rd grades/ Kansas, USA	<p>Daily PA assessed: Children wore a portable Accelerometer on a belt over the non-dominant hip for at least 10 hours on 3 days or more.</p> <p>Cardiovascular fitness: children did the PACER.</p>	<p>Academic performance: Weschler Individual Achievement Test-Third Edition (WIAT-III). It assessed reading comprehension and oral reading fluency, spelling, and mathematics problem solving and numerical operations.</p>	<p>Findings showed a direct effect of PA on AF ($b = 0.009, p < 0.001$) and an indirect effect (mediation) of PA via fitness on math achievement ($b = 0.003, p < 0.01$). However, PA nor AF were correlated with WIAT-III reading or spelling scores.</p>
[43]	CRF/AP	Cross-sectional study/ 687students/ Mean age = 7.8 ± 0.6 years from 2 nd and 3 rd grades/ Kansas USA	<p>Physical activity: To measure PA, children wore an ActiGraph GT3X+ portable accelerometer on a belt over the non-dominant hip for 4 consecutive days (including 1 weekend day)</p> <p>Cardiorespiratory fitness: To measure progressive cardiovascular fitness, PACER was used.</p>	<p>Academic performance: The WIAT-III is comprised of 16 subtests. For this study, five subtests were selected: reading comprehension, oral reading fluency, spelling, mathematics problem solving, and numerical operations.</p>	<p>Multilevel regression results for AF indicated there was no significant linear or non-linear association between fitness and reading achievement ($p > 0.05$), but a significant quadratic association between fitness and both spelling and math achievement (both p's < 0.01).</p>
[44]	Motor performance, cardiovascular performance/AP	Cross-section study/ 341 students/ 6-8 years from 1 st and 3 rd grades/ Kuopio, Finland	<p>Body composition: Body fat mass was assessed using a Lunar dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry device. Body weight was measured using a calibrated InBod. BMI (body weight (kg) divided by height (m) squared).</p>	<p>Academic performance: Reading fluency and reading comprehension were assessed using a group-administered timed subtest of the nationally normed reading achievement battery (ALLU).</p>	<p>A worse overall motor performance in grade 1, was associated with poorer reading fluency ($F_{2,161} = 5.94, p = 0.003$), reading comprehension ($F_{2,161} = 3.95, p = 0.021$), and arithmetic skills ($F_{2,161} = 10.01, p = 0.001$).</p>

Cardiorespiratory fitness:

The PA test protocol included a 3-min warm-up period, a 1-min steady-state period, a PA period with a workload increase every 6 s until exhaustion, and a 4-min cooldown period.

Motor performance:

The shuttle run test was used to assess speed and agility. The flamingo balance test was used to assess static balance. The box and block test was used to assess manual dexterity.

Arithmetic skills were assessed using a basic arithmetic test, with a set of visually presented addition and subtraction tasks.

in grades 1–3 after adjustment for age. Children who had lower motor performance in grades 1–3 had poorer reading fluency ($p = 0.003$) and reading comprehension ($p = 0.025$).

[33]

PF/EF (visual memory, working memory, attention).

Cross-sectional study/ 224 children/ Mean age 12.2 years/ Jyväskylä, Finland

Physical activity and sedentary time:

The ActiGraph GT1M/GT3X accelerometers with vertical axel were used to measure children's MVPA and sedentary time. The accelerometer was worn on the right hip with an elastic waistband during waking hours for seven consecutive days.

Visual memory:

Pattern Recognition Memory test (PRM) assessed recognition memory and visual patterns.

Executive functions

Spatial Span (SSP) and Intra-Extra Dimensional Set Shift (IED) tests assess the length of the visuospatial working memory span based on the Corsi blocks task.

Girls spent more of their waking hours being sedentary than boys. Objectively measured MVPA was negatively associated with the RTI five-choice test score (ms), whereas sedentary time was not associated with the RTI five-choice test score. Sedentary time was positively associated with RVPA, whereas objectively measured MVPA was not

				Attention: Reaction Time (RT) and Rapid Visual Information Processing (RVP) measured children's reaction time and speed of response to a visual target.	associated with RVP. Self-reported playing of computer/video games was negatively associated with SSP span length.
[45]	PF/EF (inhibition, working memory, cognitive flexibility and planning)	Cross-sectional study/ 80 students/ 8-12 years old	Physical activity: An accelerometer was used (The ActiGraph GT1M/GT3X) over seven consecutive days.	Executive functions: Inhibition: Was measured with Stroop test. Working memory: Was measured with the Visual Memory Span test. Cognitive flexibility: Was measured with Trailmaking. Planning: Children used Tower of London test in order to measure planning.	More time spent in sedentary behaviour was related to worse inhibition ($r = -0.24$). A higher total volume of PA was associated with better planning ability ($r = 0.24$) and a shorter total execution time ($r = -0.29$). A significant correlation was found between time spent in MVPA and the total execution time of the Tower of London ($r = -0.29$).
[20]	Poor CRF/ EF(attention)	Cross-sectional study/ 62 students/ 9-10 years old/ East-central Illinois region, USA	Cardiorespiratory fitness: Maximal oxygen consumption ($VO_2\max$) was measured using a computerised indirect calorimetry system with averages for oxygen uptake (VO_2) and respiratory exchange ratio (RER; $VC0_2/V0_2$) assessed every 20 seconds.	Poor attention: The ADHD Rating Scale IV is an 18-item inventory completed by the parent/legal guardian based upon the diagnostic criteria for attention deficit hyperactivity disorder Pubertal status:	Findings showed that lower-fit children exhibited poorer overall response accuracy during a task requiring aspects of cognitive control relative to their higher-fit counterparts, with a disproportionately greater number of errors of omission,

[21]

CRF/AP and EF
(way of learning
and memory)

Cross-sectional
study/ 3 days/ 48
students/ children 7-
9 years old/ Illinois,
USA

Day 1: participants completed
maximal oxygen consumption
(VO₂max) test to assess their
level of AF.

Cardiorespiratory fitness:
Sessions occurred on
consecutive days and
involved a mobile application
on an iPad (Apple Inc.,
Cupertino, CA). The task
involved remembering names
of specific regions comprised
of four letters each from a map

The Tanner Pubertal
Timing Scales use self-
ratings based upon
schematic drawings of
secondary sexual
characteristics.

Intelligent:

The K-BIT assessed the verbal
and nonverbal intelligence in
individuals.

Learning and recall:

Day 2: children learned the
names and locations of the
regions. Participants
learned two different maps
using two different
learning strategies: a study
only (SO) strategy and a test
study (TS) strategy. Day 3:
Participants returned one
day after studying the maps
to complete the recall test.

and longer, more frequent
sequential errors of omission.

There were no differences
in performance at initial
learning between higher fit
and lower fit participants.
However, during the
retention session higher fit
children outperformed lower
fit children, particularly
when the initial learning
strategy involved relatively
poor recall performance.
Fitness can boost learning
and memory of children and
these fitness-associated
performance benefits are
largest in conditions in which
initial learning is the most
challenging.

[51]

Motor ability(aerobic endurance, motor coordination, muscular strength)/EF (updating, inhibitions, shifting) and academic performance

Cross-sectional study/10 week/236 students/children 10-12 years old/Magglingen, Switzerland

The first 4 week the motor ability was evaluated.

Aerobic endurance:

The Shuttle run test was used to assess cardiorespiratory endurance.

Next 6 week the motor coordination and muscular strength was assessed

Motor coordination:

Motor coordination was measured by jumping sideways, a subtest of the Körperkordinations test für Kinder

Muscular strength

The standing long jump was used to measure strength

Executive function

Updating

A non-spatial n-back task was used to assess updating

Inhibition

A child-adapted Eriksen flanker task was used

Shifting

An additional block ("mixed" block) included in the flanker task was employed

Academic performance

Math

Arithmetic, geometry, and solving written math problems Task was considered

Reading

The Salzburger Lese-Screening für die Klassenstufen 5–8 was used

Spelling

Hamburger Schreib-Probe test was employed

A mediation analysis was used to show how EF was a mediator variable for the three physical variables . However, there was only one direct path from motor coordination and the AP. It concludes by showing an indirect path of physical skills and the AP through the EF

[48]	Team games and aerobic exercise /EF (inhibition and shifting)	Repeated measure study/ acute effect/ 12 years old/ Bern, Switzerland	<p>Team games group (floorball and basketball):</p> <p>These two team games were chosen because they are appropriate to induce MVPA intensity. Both control and complex eye-hand coordination and require goal-directed behaviour. Third, these team games were suitable for combining sport-specific skill development.</p> <p>Aerobic exercise group:</p> <p>Children were instructed to run a marathon as an entire class, whereby each child was allowed to cross off one box from a joint list after each circuit. With a circuit of 200 m.</p> <p>Control group: normal classes of PE</p>	<p>Executive functions</p> <p>Inhibition</p> <p>Was measured by means of a child-adapted Flanker task consisting of a block with 20 congruent trials (“pure” block) and a block with 20 congruent and 20 incongruent trials in a randomised order (“standard” block).</p> <p>Shifting</p> <p>Was assessed by an additional block (“mixed” block) included in the Flanker task.</p>	<p>Both interventions (team games and aerobic exercise) have a positive acute effect on children’s AF (4–5% increase in estimated VO2 max). Importantly, an improvement in shifting performance was found only in the team games and not in the aerobic exercise or control condition. Thus, the inclusion of cognitive engagement in PA seems to be the most promising type of chronic intervention to enhance EF in children.</p>
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[46]

Aerobic, coordination, and strength classes/EF (information processing speed and selective attention)	Repeated measures study / acute effect/ 195 students/ 10-13 years old/ The Netherlands	Three types of exercises in the classroom 12 minutes for each (the first 1½ min warming-up and last 30 s cooling-down were equal for all exercise types). Heart rates: during the exercise session, students wore a HR monitor: Aerobic exercise: Various well-known, easy and repetitive movements Coordination exercise: More complex movements that stressed coordinative skills, including bilateral movements and movements in which the body mid line was crossed Strength exercise: Dynamic and static body-weight exercises Control group Normal sessions in the classroom	Information processing speed: The Letter Digit Substitution Test (LDST) requires students to match letter-number pairs according to a key, which is presented on top of the sheet. The key contains nine boxes with letters and associated numbers, between 1-9. Selective attention: Students performed the D2 test. It consists of one page with 14 lines, each consisting of 47 letters 'd' and 'p'. Above and/or below each letter are 1-4 dashes displayed, either individually or in pairs.	There were no significant acute effects of exercise on information processing speed [$F(1,174) = 0.71, p = 0.40, \eta^2p = 0.00$] and selective attention [$F(1,172) = 0.91, p = 0.34, \eta^2p = 0.01$]. Likewise, type of PA did not moderate effects on information processing speed [$F(1,174) = 1.75, p = 0.18, \eta^2p = 0.02$] and selective attention [$F(1,172) = 0.60, p = 0.55, \eta^2p = 0.01$]. Pre- and post-test scores showed similar patterns on the exercise and control day, and did not differ between exercise types.
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[6]	Physical exertion, cognitive exertion, mixed cognitive and physical exertion/EF (attention)	Repeated measures study / acute effect/ 116 students/ 8-11 years old from 3 rd -5 th grades/ Rome, Italy.	<p>Physical exertion (PE): The PE consisted of continuous aerobic circuit training followed by a submaximal shuttle run exercise. This lesson was focused on the improvement of cardiovascular endurance by performing different types of gaits (fast walking, running...) without any specific coordinative request</p> <p>Cognitive exertion (CE): It consisted of a 50-min academic class about humanistic subject matters.</p> <p>Mixed physical and cognitive exertion (CPE): Basketball was used in the context of mini-games. The basketballs were used in unconventional ways with varying game rules (use of foot-eye coordination techniques with basketballs)</p>	Attention: Children, before the intervention classes and just after these, used the D2 test in order to assess pre- and post selective attention.	Exertion type × time interaction indicates the likely presence of differential effects of the exertion type on TR (total responses) and E% (precision index) variables change after intervention. Children improved their performances from pre- to post-, and to 50' post-intervention to a lower degree when exerted in CPE condition as compared with both CE and PE conditions. These results revealed that CPE exertion type led to a lower improvement of CP values over time than the two other exertion conditions
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[47]	A 4-minute high-intensity exercise/EF (attention).	Repeated measures study/ 3 weeks/ 168 students/ Children 9-11 years old from 3 rd -5 th grades/ South eastern Ontario, Canada	FUNterval activity intervention: This physical technique requires only 4 min to complete. Consists of 20 s of high-intensity activity separated by 10 s of rest, repeated 8 times. FUNterval is performed in the classroom before the academic lessons. Control group: normal academic lessons	Attention: Children did a pre-test and a post-test using the D2 test to assess selective attention.	A comparison of the D2 test performance on no-activity days demonstrated that males made a higher number of total errors (E) and E Omission than females. The effect of the intervention on attention was good. All measures of the D2 test improved from week 1 to week 2 ($p < 0.05$).
[45]	Physical games, aerobic exercise and cognitive games sessions/EF (updating, inhibition and shifting)	Repeated measures study / Acute effect/ 219 students/ children 10-12 years/ Bern, Switzerland	Physical games session: Children played three different cooperative and competitive physical games that required the activation of one or more EF dimensions. Aerobic exercise condition: PA without cognitive engagement. This condition consisted of short tasks and games requiring different forms of running Cognitive games group: The games required the activation of all EF dimensions and the level of difficulty was increased twice during the	Executive function: Updating Was assessed by a non-spatial n-back task. Several pictures of fruits were presented one after another on the screen. Inhibition Was measured by a Flanker task consisting of a block with 20 congruent and 20 incongruent trials in a randomised order. Shifting Was assessed by an additional block (shifting block) included in the Flanker task. In this block, again 20 congruent and 20	No significant effect was found in children with lower academic achievement. In children with higher academic achievement, a significant main effect for PA ($F(1,104) = 12.55, p < .01$) and also for cognitive engagement ($F(1, 104) = 4.86, p = .03$) emerged indicating that children with higher academic achievement benefitted from all interventions relative to the control condition. Post-tests showed that children with higher academic achievement in the physical games ($p < .01, d = 1.12$), in the aerobic

			<p>game by introducing new rules.</p> <p>Control group: Children made themselves comfortable on a mat and listened to an age-appropriate story.</p>	<p>incongruent trials were shown with additional rule cued.</p>	<p>exercise ($p < .01$, $d = .89$), and in the cognitive games group ($p = .02$, $d = .57$) improved significantly more than children in the control group.</p>
[50]	<p>MVPA/EF (planning, attention, simultaneous process and successive process).</p>	<p>Repeated measures study / 2 weeks/ 40 students/ Children from 4th grade/ Southwestern Ontario, Canada</p>	<p>Experimental group: They completed the cognitive function tests after an hour MVPA lesson. Testing began approximately 10 min after the end of the PE lesson and all students were tested within one hour after the end of the PE class.</p> <p>Control group: This group was tested first after PA and eight days later after no activity.</p> <p>Cardiorespiratory fitness measurement: Heart rate monitors were used to measure the intensity of PA for a randomly selected, gender-matched group of ten students in each class.</p>	<p>Children completed an independent reading task assigned by their regular teacher.</p> <p>Executive function: The PASS theory has been operationalised using the Cognitive Assessment System (CAS) which measures planning, attention, simultaneous processing, and successive processing.</p>	<p>Performance on the planning test significantly improved after PA ($p < 0.001$), controlling for sequence and habituation/retesting effects. No improvement was observed for attention, simultaneous processing, or successive processing.</p>

[55]	CRF/AP	Interventional study/ 3 years/ 1286 students/ Mean age=11.3 from 5 th , 6 th and 7 th grades/ Portugal	Participants were part of the PA and Family-Based Intervention in Paediatric Obesity Prevention in the School Settings (PESSOA project). This intervention lasted 3 years. CRF measurement: The CRF was assessed by PACER Body mass index (BMI): Was calculated by the Quetelet index (weight (kg)/height (m) ²)	Academic performance Children were assessed at baseline and at the end of 3 years by student marks (Mathematic, Portuguese, English and Science)	Being persistently fit (fit- fit), compared with those classified unfit-unfit, increased the odds of having high levels of academic achievement in Portuguese (odds ratio (OR) = 3.49; 95% CI, 1.97-6.20; p = 0.001) and foreign language (OR = 2.41; 95% CI, 1.39-4.14; p = 0.01) at follow-up. Students that improved their CRF and became fit (unfit-fit) also had higher odds of achieving better marks than those persistently unfit-unfit in Portuguese (p = 0.01) and foreign language (p = 0.01).
[54]	Increasing classes/AP	PE Interventional study / 1965 students/ elementary school/ Sweden	Experimental group: Children were carrying out a Swedish government programme (Handslaget), using group play, and other activities. Control group: Student did not increase PA sessions.	Academic performance: National goals in Swedish, Mathematics, and English. Academic results from the years prior to and during the intervention programme were analysed.	Higher proportions of students in the experimental group achieved the national goals in all 3 subjects compared with the control group which obtain lower results.

- [52] Active academic lesson/AP Interventional study/ 1 year/ 228 children (122 boys and 106 girls) /Mean age: 8.1 from 2nd or 3rd grades/ Netherlands
- Experiment group:
Children have to do MVPA during F&V lessons (Fit & Vaardig op school; Fit and academically proficient at school) in the classroom (jumping while spelling words, moving around the class saying exercise results, etc.)
- Control group:
Normal lesson without PA
- Academic performance:
Observations were done during the lesson. Investigators observed whether children performed the basic exercise (on-task), the specific exercise (on-task) or no/other exercise (off-task) of maths and languages.
- The third-grade children in the intervention group scored significantly higher on both mathematics ($F[1,99] = 11.72$, $p < .05$) and reading ($F[1,98] = 6.97$, $p < .05$) in comparison with the third-grade children in the control group. On the other hand, the second-grade children in the intervention group scored significantly lower on mathematics in comparison with the second-grade children in the control group ($F[1,109] = 12.40$, $p < .05$). No differences were found on the reading test in grade 2 ($F[1,109] = 0.72$, $p = .40$)
- [53] Active academic lessons/AP Interventional study/ 20 week/ 29 students/ Mean age: 8.87 from 3rd grade/ Kentucky, USA
- Experimental group:
Intervention children had PA breaks for 20+ minutes per day. Children combined different PA like teacher-directed instruction, partner or group exercises around the classroom, etc. To measure school day PA, participants wore a pedometer for five consecutive school days
- Academic performance
Reading fluency was curriculum-based while mathematical fluency was assessed with short progress measures designed to assess children's reading and mathematical abilities. At the beginning and end of the intervention, students
- The intervention group ($M = 24.56$, $SD = 2.21$) scored significantly higher in mathematics than the control group ($M = 13.69$, $SD = 2.45$). The scores in reading were statistically higher than standardised test scores ($p < .001$).

Control group:
They did normal academic classes in the classroom

carried out the Test of Primary Reading Outcomes (T-PRO), which assesses phonics, vocabulary, comprehension, and research skills.

[56]

Afterschool PA/ Behaviour (accuracy and reaction time) and (modulated attentional, inhibition and cognitive flexibility).
PA/ 9 months/ 221 students/ 7-9 years old/ East Central Illinois EF

Aerobic fitness:
A test of maximal oxygen consumption (VO₂max) was used to measure AF.
Afterschool PA programme:
The 2-hour PA intervention occurred after each school day, and focused on improvement of AF. Children intermittently participated in at least 70 minutes of MVPA. The intervention included 30-40 minutes at PA stations. Next, a healthy snack and educational component were provided as a rest period, and children then engaged in low organisational games (45-55 minutes) centred on a skill theme.

Attentional inhibition
Assessed using a modified flanker task. Cognitive flexibility was assessed by using a colour-shape switch task. A modified flanker task is a method to measure inhibition in which children are engaged in a series of trials that, in this case, have arrays of fish that either match (congruent arrays) or do not match (incongruent arrays).

Response accuracy increased in both groups, however, the intervention group demonstrated greater improvement from pre-test to post-test than the wait-list control group (3.2%, 95% CI: 0.0 to 6.5, $d = 0.27$ for group difference in pre-to-post change score. The improvement in performance on the heterogeneous task was greater among intervention participants (4.8%, 95% CI: 1.1 to 8.4, $d = 0.35$ for group difference in pre-to-post change score.

- [57] Increasing hours of PE/EF (spatial memory, working memory) and attention
- Interventional study/ 10 week/ 185 students/ Mean age: 6.2/ Glasgow, Scotland
- Physical activity: Data were collected at week 0 with the Actigraph GT1M accelerometer for 7 days. Actigraphs were worn over the right hip on a waist belt.
- Experimental group: It increased 2 classes per week of PE.
- Control group: Only 1 class of PE per week
- Cognitive function: The Cognitive Assessment System (CAS), the Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Battery (CANTAB).
- Attention: The Attention Network Test (ANT).
- Memory: The test of Spatial Memory Span (SSP) and the test of Spatial Working Memory (SWM).
- Total PA was significantly greater during the intervention than control sessions (median difference 649 counts per minute; $p < 0.001$). There were no significant between group differences in any of the CAS scales (all $p > 0.05$). The CANTAB Spatial Working Memory Error rate was significantly reduced in the intervention group. Scores on subscales which measure the risk of suffering cognitive Problems/ Inattention, Hyperactivity and ADHD index were significantly lower post intervention than in the control group.
- [58] Afterschool PA/EF (working memory)
- Interventional study/ 9 months/ 43 students/ children 7-9 years old/ Illinois, USA
- Physical activity intervention: It occurred for a 2-hour period following each school day, and focused on improvement of CRF. Muscle fitness was addressed at least 2 days a week, with the participants using their own Thera-bands®. The sessions were around 40
- Working memory: A modified Sternberg task asked participants to encode a memory set containing an array of one, three, or five letters and press one of two buttons with their thumbs corresponding to whether a single probe letter was
- The PA intervention led to increases in CRF and improved Sternberg task performance. Further, the beneficial effects of the PA intervention were greater for a task condition requiring greater working memory demands. In addition, the intervention group exhibited

			<p>min, however there were lessons lasting 70 min.</p> <p>Cardiorespiratory fitness: Maximal oxygen consumption (VO_{2max}) was measured using a motor-driven treadmill and a modified Balke protocol.</p>	<p>present (right) or absent (left) in the encoded letter array.</p>	<p>larger initial contingent negative variation (CNV) at the frontal electrode site, relative to the control group.</p>
[59]	<p>Afterschool PA/EF(working memory)</p>	<p>Interventional study/ 10 weeks/ 71 students/ Mean age: 9.4 years/ Westphalia, Germany</p>	<p>The experimental groups had 3 afterschool sessions per week for 45 min.</p> <p>The cardiovascular exercise group (CE): Children focused on improvement of cardiovascular fitness through running and running-based games of MVPA (recorded on three occasions by F1 Polar HR monitors).</p> <p>The motor exercise group (ME): Children focused on the improvement the bilateral coordination, hand-eye coordination, and leg-arm coordination exercises as well as spatial orientation and reaction to moving objects/persons</p> <p>Control group (CO): normal PE classes</p>	<p>Working memory: Children used The Letter Digit Span (LDS). The task involves a standardised auditory presentation of an increasing mixed series of alternating numbers and letters. After an acoustic signal, each participant was asked to respond by first writing the numbers in order from the smallest to the largest, followed by writing the letters in alphabetical order.</p>	<p>Improvements in working memory from pre- to post-test in the two exercise groups were found with large effect sizes (CE: $F(1,26) = 19.709$, $p = 0.001$, $r = 0.66$; ME: $F(1,22) = 62.718$, $p = 0.001$, $r = 0.86$), but not in the CO ($F(1,20) = 0.769$, $p = 0.391$, $r = 0.19$). In the post measurement, only the ME differed significantly from the CO ($t(68) = 2.521$, $p = 0.014$, $r = 0.29$), but not from the CE ($t(68) = 0.746$, $p = 0.458$, $r = 0.09$), nor did the CE differ significantly from the CO ($t(68) = 1.887$, $p = 0.063$, $r = 0.22$).</p>

- [60] Active academic lesson/EF (inhibition, cognitive flexibility and working memory). Intervention study/ 2 years/ 499 students/ Mean age: 8.1 years from 2nd and 3rd grades/ Northern Netherlands
- Intervention group:
 Three F&V lessons per week. The F&V lessons had a duration of 20–30 min, with 10–15 min spent on solving mathematical problems and 10–15 min spent on language. They had MVPA intensity. During the F&V lessons all children started with performing a basic exercise, such as jogging, hopping in place or marching. A specific exercise was performed when the children solved an academic task.
- Control group:
 Normal lesson in the classroom
- Executive function measurement:
 Inhibition: The Golden Stroop test was used to measure inhibition.
 Cognitive flexibility: Measured using a modified version of the Wisconsin card sorting test (M-WCST)
 Working memory: The Digit span backward and Visual span backward were used.
- A great improvement in speed-coordination ($B = -0.70$, $p = 0.002$) and a lower improvement in static strength ($B = -0.92$, $p < 0.001$) were found for the intervention group. There was no significant result between intervention group and EF.
- [61] Active academic lesson/EF (inhibition, cognitive flexibility and working memory). Intervention study/ 10 months/ 449 students/ children 10-11 years old/ Stavanger, Norway.
- Aerobic fitness:
 A 10-minute interval running test was using to assess AF
- Interventional group:
 A weekly intervention was carried out of 2×45 minutes physically active academic lessons, 5×10 minutes physically active
- Executive function measurement:
 Inhibition: This EF was measured by The Golden Stroop test.
 Cognitive flexibility: Measured using the Trail Making Test
 Working memory:
- No significant differences were found between aerobic capacity and EF $F(1,344)=3.64$, $P=.057$. However, the results were positive.

			breaks and 5×10 minutes physically active homework.		The Digit span was used to measure attention capacity
			Control group: Children followed a normal routine		
[62]	Increasing hours of PE /Psychomotor function and EF (attention, working memory)	Intervention study/11 week / 931 children 10-11 years old/ Southern Denmark	Intervention group: Two weekly PE sessions based on The “FIFA 11 for Health” were added: a 45-minute “play football” session (teaching football skills and playing small-sided football) and a 45-minute “play fair” session (teaching a health message and health behaviours) Control group: This group performed the obligatory daily school-based PA (5 × 45 minutes per week).	Cognitive assessment: English version of the Cogstate® Brief Battery, which is an objective computer-based cognitive test battery addressing psychomotor function, attention, working memory and visual learning in children.	This study provided evidence that the school-based physical activity programme “FIFA 11 for Health” for Europe can improve cognitive performance in schoolchildren: psychomotor function (56, $s_x = 22$ ms, $p < .001$), attention (39, $s_x = 17$ ms, $p = .012$) and working memory (79, $s_x = 35$ ms, $p = .020$)

Note: PA = Physical activity; PF = Physical fitness; PE = Physical education; MVPA = moderate to vigorous physical activity; AF = Aerobic fitness; CRF = Cardiorespiratory fitness; PLACER = Progressive Aerobic Cardiovascular Endurance Run; BMI = Body mass index; AP = Academic performance; EF = Executive function